

Cyclic voltammetric investigations of copper(II) complexes with various imidazoles in dimethylformamide

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Abstract : The cyclic voltammetric behaviour of copper(II) complexes with various imidazoles, viz. imidazole (ImH), 2-methylimidazole (2-MeIm), 1,2-dimethylimidazole (1,2-Me₂Im) and benzimidazole (BzIm) has been investigated in dimethylformamide (DMF) containing 0.1 M tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate (TBAP) as a supporting electrolyte at a glassy carbon electrode (GCE). All these copper(II) complexes revealed a diffusion-controlled quasi-reversible one-electron transfer process (Cu^{2+/+}). It has been observed that the reduction peak potential becomes less positive (difficult reduction) with increasing concentration of a given ligand. The observed reduction potentials of these complexes become more positive in the order : Im → 2-MeIm → 1,2-Me₂Im → BzIm. The deviation of reduction potentials from the expected trend based on pK_a values of the ligands is attributed to the dominance of steric effects over the electronic effects (i.e. inductive effects) in the case of 2-MeIm and 1,2-Me₂Im ligands.

Keywords : Cyclic voltammetry, electrochemistry, imidazoles, copper(II) complexes.

Introduction

The imidazole ring, as a histidine moiety, and the benzimidazole ring, particularly as its 5,6-dimethyl derivative, function as ligands toward transition metal ions in a variety of biologically important molecules including iron-heme systems, vitamin B₁₂ and its derivatives and several metallo-proteins¹. The effectiveness of the imidazole group to act as a metal binding site has been attributed to its great fluxibility, its availability at physiological pH (pK_a ca. 7.0) and its capacity to form both σ- and π-bonds with metal ions². Schugar *et al.*³ have reported the electronic spectra for tetrakis complexes of Cu^{II} with various imidazole ligands in 1 : 4 and 1 : 8 metal : ligand ratios in methanol. On the basis of their spectroscopic results it was concluded that the formation of [Cu(ImH)₄]²⁺ is fairly complete when the ligand to Cu^{II} ratio is 4 : 1 and effectively 100% when this ratio is increased to 8 : 1. An EPR characterization of the various species [Cu(ImH)₅]²⁺ and [Cu(ImH)₆]²⁺ present in the copper(II)-imidazole (ImH) system and analogous complexes has been reported by Siddiqui and Shephard⁴. In contrast to Siddiqui *et al.*⁴, the room temperature EPR spectrum with a low molar ratio, [Cu²⁺] : [imidazole] = 1 : 10 revealed⁵ the features of two absorbing species, probably [Cu(ImH)₃]²⁺ and [Cu(ImH)₄]²⁺. The experimental results at higher molar ratios, 1 : 100 and 1 : 200

at both room and low temperatures gave evidence of the formation of well characterized four-coordinate species⁵, [Cu(ImH)₄]²⁺ in which central metal ion is bonded through N atoms of imidazoles.

We have, therefore, decided to undertake the investigation of the cyclic voltammetric behaviour of Cu^{II} complexes with various imidazole ligands in different Cu^{II} : ligand molar ratios in dimethylformamide (DMF) containing 0.1 M tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate (TBAP) as a supporting electrolyte. The overall aim of this work is to correlate the redox potentials of these complexes with the electronic and steric effects of the substituted imidazole ligands.

Results and discussion

The cyclic voltammetric behaviour of the copper(II) complexes with various imidazole ligands in five different copper(II) : ligand molar ratios, 1 : 2, 1 : 4, 1 : 6, 1 : 10 and 1 : 100 {ligand = imidazole (ImH), 2-methylimidazole (2-MeIm), 1,2-dimethylimidazole (1,2-Me₂Im) and benzimidazole (BzIm)} has been investigated in DMF/0.1 M TBAP media at a glassy carbon electrode in scan rate range 10 to 300 mV s⁻¹. The cyclic voltammetric results for all these complexes at 25 mV s⁻¹ are summarized in Table 1, while for benzimidazole complexes in 1 : 10 and 1 : 100 molar ratios at different scan

Table 1. CV parameters for copper(II) complexes with various imidazoles in DMF/0.1 M TBAP at scan rate = 25 mV s⁻¹

Ligand (L)	[Cu ^{II}] : [L] molar ratio	E_{pc_1} (mV)	E_{pa_1} (mV)	E^0 (mV)	ΔE_p (mV)	I_{pa_1}/I_{pc_1}
ImH	1 : 2	+260	+395	+328	135	0.90
	1 : 4	+235	+340	+288	105	0.80
	1 : 6	+200	+300	+250	100	0.80
	1 : 10	+170	+275	+223	105	0.80
	1 : 100	+10	+80	+45	70	0.88
2-MeIm	1 : 2	+315	+425	+370	110	0.90
	1 : 4	+275	+370	+322	95	0.90
	1 : 6	+255	+350	+302	95	0.95
	1 : 10	+220	+305	+265	95	0.80
	1 : 100	+105	+195	+150	90	0.88
1,2-Me ₂ Im	1 : 2	+325	+480	+403	155	0.90
	1 : 4	+285	+410	+348	125	0.90
	1 : 6	+270	+400	+338	130	0.80
	1 : 10	+240	+365	+303	125	0.80
	1 : 100	+135	+245	+185	100	0.85
BzIm	1 : 2	+375	+470	+423	95	0.90
	1 : 4	+340	+440	+390	100	0.80
	1 : 6	+315	+415	+365	100	0.80
	1 : 10	+300	+395	+348	95	0.88
	1 : 100	+165	+255	+210	90	0.85

$$E^0 = \frac{1}{2}(E_{pa_1} + E_{pc_1})$$

rates are given in Table 2. It should be noted that the electrochemical behaviour for all these complexes are similar. A negative going scan in the potential range +0.80 to -0.40 V vs SCE shows a well-defined redox couple (c_1/a_1) for all the systems studied. The cyclic voltammogram for 1 : 100 Cu^{II} : BzIm system at 25 mV s⁻¹ is given in Fig. 1. The plot of cathodic peak current (I_{pc_1}) vs square root of the scan rate ($v^{1/2}$) gives a straight line passing through origin. Constant potential coulometry at +10 mV vs Ag/AgCl (in 1 : 100 ratio) has confirmed that the reduction process involves a single electron per molecule of the complex. The redox process of these complexes is found to be chemically reversible since I_{pa_1}/I_{pc_1} is nearly 1.0, but electrochemically quasi-reversible since anodic to cathodic peak potential difference $\Delta E_p > 60$ mV and its magnitude increases with increasing scan rate (Table 2). On the basis of these observations, it is therefore concluded that the reduction of all these complexes involves a diffusion-controlled quasi-reversible one-electron transfer reaction^{6,7}.

It may be noted that the cathodic peak potential (E_{pc_1}) shifts cathodically (i.e., becomes less positive) with increasing concentration of a given ligand (Table 1). This indicates that the reduction becomes more difficult with increasing concentration of the ligand. This is probably because of the formation of higher order complex species³⁻⁵, $[CuL_n]^{2+}$ at higher concentration of ligands. This is also supported by ESR characterization of various species present in Cu^{II}-imidazole systems reported earlier^{4,5}.

The pK_a values⁸ of the neutral form of the ligands increase in the sequence : BzIm (5.4) < ImH (6.95) < 2-MeIm (7.75) < 1,2-Me₂Im. The strength of a metal-ligand bond, as reflected in the stability constants of the reactions $M + L \rightarrow ML$, is directly correlated with ligand basicity (pK_a), as has frequently been observed⁹. These values reflect both the basicity (a σ effect) as well as the electron-withdrawing abilities (a π effect) of the ligand¹⁰. In fact, the copper(II)-ligand formation constants are not reduced seriously by imidazole alkylation^{3,11}. The methyl group(s) (a σ -donor in the 2-MeIm and 1,2-Me₂Im)

Table 2. CV parameters for 1 : 10 and 1 : 100 Cu^{II}-BzIm systems in 0.1 M TBAP/DMF at different scan rates

Scan rate (mV s ⁻¹)	E_{pc_1} (mV)	E_{pa_1} (mV)	E^0 (mV)	ΔE_p (mV)	I_{pa_1}/I_{pc_1}
L = 10 mM					
10	+310	+395	+353	85	1.0
25	+300	+395	+348	95	0.88
50	+295	+405	+350	110	0.83
100	+275	+405	+340	130	0.80
150	+270	+415	+342	145	0.85
200	+270	+420	+345	150	0.78
250	+260	+425	+343	165	0.82
300	+255	+430	+343	175	0.78
L = 100 mM					
10	+180	+250	+215	70	1.0
25	+165	+255	+210	90	0.85
50	+165	+255	+210	90	0.80
100	+160	+265	+213	105	0.85
150	+155	+265	+210	110	0.87
200	+150	+270	+210	120	0.88
250	+150	+275	+213	125	0.85
300	+150	+275	+213	125	0.85

increases the electron density on the nitrogen atoms of the ligands with respect to ImH. The reverse argument applies for the electron-withdrawing nature of the fused benzene ring of the BzIm. Because 1,2-Me₂Im is most basic amongst these imidazole ligands, the increased electron density at the core nitrogens is expected to result in most difficult reduction (i.e., least positive reduction potential) of the Cu^{II}-1,2-Me₂Im complex. On the otherhand, reverse argument applies for the Cu^{II}-BzIm complex, i.e., least difficult to reduce (i.e., most positive reduction potential). On the basis of basicity (pK_a) of these ligands alone, one expects that the reduction potentials of the Cu^{II} complexes with these imidazole ligands should become more positive in the order : 1,2-Me₂Im → 2-MeIm → ImH → BzIm. However, the observed reduction potentials at a given M : L molar ratio increase (i.e., become more positive) in the order : ImH → 2-MeIm → 1,2-Me₂Im → BzIm (Table 1). The deviation of reduction potentials from the expected trend based on pK_a values is attributed to the dominance of steric effects over the electronic effects (i.e., inductive effects) in the case of 2-MeIm and 1,2-Me₂Im ligands.

Experimental

The details of electrochemical measurements have al-

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammogram of 1 : 100 Cu^{II}-BzIm system in DMF/0.1 M TBAP at $v = 25 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$.

ready been described in our previous publications⁷. All measurements were made at 25 °C. GCE, SCE ($E^0 = +242 \text{ mV vs NHE}$) and platinum wire were used as working, reference and auxiliary electrodes, respectively. Coulometric measurements were made using BAS Elec-

trochemical System Model EPSILON using carbon vitrous electrode as working electrode, Ag/AgCl as reference electrode and coiled platinum wire as auxillary electrode. All the chemicals used were obtained from commercial sources. The solutions under investigations were freshly prepared by dissolving $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and a given ligand in DMF in stoichiometric amounts. The concentration of metal salt was kept constant (1.0 millimole) in each case.

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